

Summation Formulas for Negative-Indexed Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers

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Abstract

This paper investigates summation formulas for Fibonacci and Lucas numbers with negative indices. The goal is to derive explicit expressions for these sums and to identify structural patterns.

1 Introduction

Although Fibonacci and Lucas numbers are traditionally defined only for non-negative indices, both sequences can be consistently extended to negative integers.

Fibonacci numbers F_n (OEIS: A000045) [1] are defined recursively as:

$$F_0 = 0, \quad F_1 = 1, \quad F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2} \quad \text{for } n \geq 2$$

Negative Fibonacci numbers F_{-n} (OEIS A039834) [2] satisfy the following relation:

$$F_{-n} = F_{-(n+2)} + F_{-(n+1)} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

Equivalently, [3]

$$F_{-n} = (-1)^{n+1} F_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

Lucas numbers L_n (OEIS A000032) [4] are defined recursively as:

$$L_0 = 2, \quad L_1 = 1, \quad L_n = L_{n-1} + L_{n-2} \quad \text{for } n \geq 2$$

The recursive relation for the negative Lucas numbers L_{-n} is:

$$L_{-n} = L_{-(n+2)} + L_{-(n+1)} \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

Hence, [5]

$$L_{-n} = (-1)^n L_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

2 Summation Formulas for negative Fibonacci Numbers

Theorem 1.1:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \sum_{k=0}^n F_{-k} = 1 - F_{-(n-1)}$$

Proof 1.1:

The identity can be established by mathematical induction. These calculations verify the identity for the first two cases.

$$\sum_{k=0}^0 F_{-k} = F_0 = 0 = 1 - F_{-(-1)} = 1 - 1 = 0$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^1 F_{-k} = F_0 + F_{-1} = 1 = 1 - F_{-(1-1)} = 1$$

(BC)

Induction Hypothesis: Following holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-k} = 1 - F_{-(n-1)}$$

(IH)

Now we verify that the identity holds for $n + 1$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n+1} F_{-k} = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-k} \right) + F_{-(n+1)} = 1 - F_{-(n-1)} + F_{-(n+1)} = 1 - F_{-n}$$

Therefore, to complete the proof, it must be shown that the following equation holds true.

$$1 - (F_{-(n-1)} - F_{-(n+1)}) = 1 - F_{-n}$$

From the recurrence relation it follows that

$$F_{-(n-1)} = F_{-(n+1)} + F_{-n}$$

Now, substitute this expression into the original equation:

$$1 - ((F_{-(n+1)} + F_{-n}) - F_{-(n+1)}) = 1 - F_{-n}$$

Simplifying the left-hand side:

$$1 - F_{-n} = 1 - F_{-n}$$

(IS)

This shows that the equation holds true, thus completing the proof.

□

Theorem 1.2:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=1}^n (F_{-k})^2 = F_n F_{n+1}$$

Proof 1.2:

We use the known identities for Fibonacci numbers [6]:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F_k^2 = F_n F_{n+1}$$

And:

$$F_{-k} = (-1)^{k+1} F_k$$

Therefore:

$$F_{-k}^2 = ((-1)^{k+1} F_k)^2 = F_k^2$$

Hence:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F_{-k}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n F_k^2 = F_n F_{n+1}$$

□

Theorem 1.3:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n F_{-2k} = -F_{2n+1} + 1$$

Proof 1.3:

Base Case $n = 0$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^0 F_{-2k} = -F_{2*0+1} + 1 = 0$$

Base Case $n = 1$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^1 F_{-2k} = -F_{2*1+1} + 1 = -1$$

(BC)

Induction Hypothesis: Following holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-2k} = -F_{2n+1} + 1$$

(IH)

Inductive Step:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n+1} F_{-2k} = -F_{(2n+2)+1} + 1$$

$$\left(\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-2k} \right) + F_{-2(n+1)} = (-F_{2n+1} + 1) + F_{-2(n+1)} = -F_{2n+3} + 1$$

Using the identity:

$$F_{-2k} = (-1)^{2k+1} F_{2k} = -F_{2k}$$

It can be said that:

$$-F_{2n+1} - F_{2n+2} + 1 = -F_{2n+3} + 1$$

Multiplying both sides with -1 , yields

$$F_{2n+1} + F_{2n+2} - 1 = F_{2n+3} - 1$$

$$F_{2n+1} + F_{2n+2} = F_{2n+3}$$

And this is the known identity for Fibonacci numbers and thus completing the proof.

(IS)

□

Theorem 1.4:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} F_{-k} = F_n$$

Proof 1.4:

Using the Binet Formula for Fibonacci Numbers [7]:

$$F_n = \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\sqrt{5}}$$

Where:

$$\alpha = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad \beta = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}$$

and the identity for negative Fibonacci numbers:

$$F_{-n} = (-1)^{n+1} F_n = (-1)^{n+1} \left(\frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\sqrt{5}} \right)$$

$$S := \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} F_{-k}$$

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} (\alpha^k - \beta^k) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} \alpha^k - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} \beta^k \right)$$

Because of [8]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} z^k = (1 + z)^n$$

For the first sum, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} \alpha^k = - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-\alpha)^k = -(1-\alpha)^n$$

Similarly,

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} \beta^k = -(1-\beta)^n$$

Therefore,

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} (-(1-\alpha)^n + (1-\beta)^n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} ((1-\beta)^n - (1-\alpha)^n)$$

Using $1-\beta = \alpha$ and $1-\alpha = \beta$, we obtain

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} (\alpha^n - \beta^n) = F_n$$

□

Theorem 1.5.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n F_{-(k+n)} = F_{-(n-2)} - F_{-(2n-1)}.$$

Proof 1.5. Using the identity of Theorem 1.1.

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-k} = 1 - F_{-(n-1)},$$

Spiting the sum as

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_{-(k+n)} = \sum_{m=n}^{2n} F_{-m} = \sum_{m=0}^{2n} F_{-m} - \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} F_{-m}.$$

Applying the formula from Theorem 1.1 gives

$$(1 - F_{-(2n-1)}) - (1 - F_{-(n-2)}) = F_{-(n-2)} - F_{-(2n-1)}.$$

□

3 Summation Formulas for negative Lucas Numbers

Theorem 2.1:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n L_{-k} = 3 - L_{-(n-1)}$$

Proof 2.1:

Base Case $n = 0$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^0 L_{-k} = 2 = 3 - L_1 = 3 - 1$$

Base Case $n = 1$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^1 L_{-k} = 1 = 3 - L_0 = 3 - 2$$

(BC)

Induction Hypothesis: Following holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-k} = 3 - L_{-(n-1)}$$

(IH)

Inductive Step

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n+1} L_{-k} = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-k} \right) + L_{-(n+1)} = 3 - L_{-(n-1)} + L_{-(n+1)}$$

To complete the proof, following equation must hold true:

$$3 - (L_{-(n-1)} - L_{-(n+1)}) = 3 - L_{-n}$$

From the definition of the recursive behavior following can be derived:

$$L_{-(n-1)} = L_{-(n+1)} + L_{-n}$$

Now, substitute this expression into the original equation:

$$3 - ((L_{-(n+1)} + L_{-n}) - L_{-(n+1)}) = 3 - L_{-n}$$

Simplifying the left-hand side:

$$3 - (L_{-n}) = 3 - L_{-n}$$

(IS)

□

Theorem 2.2:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=1}^n (L_{-k})^2 = L_n L_{n+1} - 2$$

Proof 2.2: Using the well known identities:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n L_k^2 = L_n L_{n+1} - 2$$

and [5]

$$L_{-n} = (-1)^n L_n$$

We can derive the following:

$$(L_{-n})^2 = ((-1)^n L_n)^2 = (L_n)^2$$

Substituting in the formula:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n L_{-k}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n L_k^2 = L_n L_{n+1} - 2$$

□

Theorem 2.3:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n L_{-2k} = L_{2n+1} + 1$$

Proof 2.3 :

Base Case $n = 0$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^0 L_{-2k} = L_{2*0+1} + 1 = 1 + 1 = 2$$

Base Case $n = 1$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^1 L_{-2k} = L_{2*1+1} + 1 = 4 + 1 = 5$$

(BC)

Induction Hypothesis: Following holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-2k} = L_{2n+1} + 1$$

(IH)

Inductive Step:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n+1} L_{-2k} = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-2k} \right) + L_{-(2n+2)} = L_{2n+1} + L_{-(2n+2)} + 1 = L_{2n+3} + 1$$

Using the known identity of:

$$L_{-2n} = (-1)^{2n} L_{2n} = L_{2n}$$

$$L_{2n+1} + L_{2n+2} + 1 = L_{2n+3} + 1$$

This is a known identity for Lucas Numbers thus completing the Proof.

(IS)

□

Theorem 2.4:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} L_{-k} = L_n$$

Proof 2.4: The equivalent to the Binet formula for Lucas Numbers [7]:

$$L_n = \alpha^n + \beta^n$$

Where:

$$\alpha = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad \beta = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}$$

And for negative Lucas numbers it is:

$$L_{-n} = (-1)^n (\alpha^n + \beta^n)$$

Defining S:

$$S := \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} L_{-k}$$

Using the generating formula:

$$S = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k (\alpha^k + \beta^k) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \alpha^k + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \beta^k$$

This is equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \alpha^k &= (1 - \alpha)^n \\ \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \beta^k &= (1 - \beta)^n \\ S &= (1 - \alpha)^n + (1 - \beta)^n \\ S &= \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n + \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n = L_n \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.5.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \sum_{k=0}^n L_{-(k+n)} = L_{-(n-2)} - L_{-(2n-1)}.$$

Proof 2.5. Using the identity of Theorem 2.1:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-k} = 3 - L_{-(n-1)},$$

splitting the sum as

$$\sum_{k=0}^n L_{-(k+n)} = \sum_{m=n}^{2n} L_{-m} = \sum_{m=0}^{2n} L_{-m} - \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} L_{-m}.$$

Applying the formula from Theorem 2.1 gives

$$(3 - L_{-(2n-1)}) - (3 - L_{-(n-2)}) = L_{-(n-2)} - L_{-(2n-1)}.$$

□

References

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